

CO₂-SPICER - CO₂ Storage Pilot In a CarbonatE Reservoir

R4.2 Report on geomechanical data to be stored in the project database

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1 INTRODUCTION

The main objective of the report is to give a complete overview of the methods used and the associated geomechanical data collected in CO₂-SPICER - WP4. The data will be subsequently stored in the project geodatabase. The chapters of the report aim to:

- describe and discuss the methods that were used to measure or estimate the data
- demonstrate the data that were collected in WP4,
- introduce the formats, in which the data will be available in the project geodatabase

An overview of all results of Work Package 4 (Geomechanical Characteristics) is provided here. The raw data is stored in a large Excel-document where all tables and figures are captured from. The interpretations and applications of these results are provided in the follow-up result R4.3, the interlinked work packages (WPs) and the Milestone M4.1 document on handover of WP4 results to WP3. Further, the results will be applied in WP6 on risk assessment and as a constraint on the further scenarios evaluated in WP8.

The storage complex must be characterized geomechanically to ensure safe storage of the injected CO₂. The re-pressurization and cooling lead to effective stress changes that is compared to the strength obtained of the reservoir and overburden rock types. In addition to assessment of the above phenomena, we have also evaluated if any changes are observed in the sound velocity before and after samples were exposed to CO₂ at in-situ stress and pressure conditions.

Core samples acquired from the Zar-3 field are stored in the MND core repository. A series of drill cores were acquired from the different wells from the wider area of Zar-3 site and stored in 1 m long wooden boxes; one core is usually stored in more boxes. In general, only core material of sufficient size, i.e. with fragments that survived the coring, handling and storage could be used for geomechanical assessment (see Chapter 6 for discussion). The identification of each sample were: “Wellid_core#_box#_smplid”. The 78 individual samples for geomechanical testing are shown in in Tab. 1-1. Each test is identified uniquely, as several samples were, sometimes, acquired from the same box. Each box is uniquely identified by its number, core number and name of “source” well.

Tab. 1-1: Overview of the number of rock samples in the WP4 geomechanical data base and subsequent age, lithostratigraphy, and type.

Age	Lithostratigraphy	Type	Number of rock samples
Upper Jurassic	Mikulov Fm.	Seal	9
Paleogene	Žarošice Mb.	Seal	9
Upper Jurassic	Vranovice Fm. Kurdějov (Ernstbrunn Fm?)	Reservoir - possible analogue	1
Upper Jurassic	Vranovice Fm. (Nikolčice Fm.)	Reservoir	1
Upper Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	50
Lower Carboniferous (sandstones)	Myslejovice Fm.	Seal	8

2 LIST OF SYMBOLS

symp.	quantity	unit
a	p-q model parameter	-
α	thermal expansion coefficient	K ⁻¹
b	cohesion	Pa
c	compressibility	Pa ⁻¹
d	diameter	m
h	height	m
g	gravitational acceleration	m ² .s ⁻¹
l	length	m
r	radius	m
v	velocity	m.s ⁻¹
E	Young's modulus	Pa
K	bulk modulus	Pa
P	pressure	Pa
T	temperature	K
TS	tensile strength	Pa
UCS	unconfined compressive strength	Pa
V	volume	m ³
α_B	Biot's coefficient	-
α_T	Thermal expansion coefficient	-
ε	strain	-
ν	Poisson's ratio	-
σ	normal stress	Pa
τ	shear stress	Pa
$s_{1,2,3}$	Stresses along principal direction	MPa

φ	angle of internal friction	°
ϕ	porosity	-
ψ	p-q model parameter	°
List of symbol's subscripts		
a	axial	
b	bulk	
bc	of bulk volume with change of confining pressure	
bp	of bulk volume with change of pore pressure	
c	confining	
pc	of pore volume with change of confining pressure	
dyn	dynamic	
m	rock matrix	
p	pore in volume	
r	radial	
s	static	
v	volumetric	
P	pressure wave in velocity	

3 THEORY

This section describes the theoretical basis for how geomechanical parameters are extracted from geomechanical tests. We also go through the practical experimental methods.

3.1 Basic premises for geomechanical assessment – defining strength and stress

A strength parameter of a rock specimen defines a stress magnitude at which the specimen fails under a specified type of stress. The different modes of failure are described in failure envelopes and occurring at different stress states. For each type of failure, the critical stresses are given. There are typically three failure modes studied here: hydrostatic compression, tensional failure, and shear failure.

In three dimension the stress state is defined via the second rank stress tensor σ with 9 coefficients

$$\sigma = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{xx} & \tau_{xy} & \tau_{xz} \\ \tau_{yx} & \sigma_{yy} & \tau_{yz} \\ \tau_{zx} & \tau_{zy} & \sigma_{zz} \end{pmatrix}$$

The stress tensor can be transformed by a change of the basis of the matrix, which results in the transformed matrix having non-zero elements only on its diagonal. The new basis gives us the direction in which no shear stresses τ act on a rock and normal stresses σ are the only non-zero elements. The direction and magnitude of these principal stresses can be obtained by calculating eigenvectors and eigenvalues of the original stress tensor:

$$\sigma = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{xx} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_{yy} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \sigma_{zz} \end{pmatrix}$$

Fig. 3-1: Mohr's circles for an anisotropic three-dimensional stress state.

Principal stresses can be denoted by decreasing index with decreasing magnitude as $\sigma_1 \geq \sigma_2 \geq \sigma_3$. In a field case, the principal stresses are obtained by a rotation of the stress vector. Further, it is typical that the highest principal stress is vertical, and the two other stresses are horizontal.

As the strength of a rock can be expressed by one parameter only for a specific stress state as the strength of the rock (in the sense defined above) changes with the stress state. A frequently used representation of a stress state is the Mohr's circle. It is constructed in the $\sigma - \tau$ space and represents a transformation for a plane stress problem. By choosing an orientation relative to a principal stress (horizontal axis) we can illustrate the magnitude of normal and shear stresses acting in a plane in that direction. The symbol τ describe the shear stress projected onto a 2D plan in the 3D stress vector, and the symbol σ represent the normal component on this plane. When the plane is rotated, we get the Mohr circles in Fig. 3-1.

Laboratory programme of WP4 aims to establish a stability region by drawing a failure envelope in the $\sigma - \tau$ space that encapsulates the area of stress states where the rock is

stable/reversible upon loading-unloading. One of the models representing the brittle failure of a rock is the Mohr-Coulomb failure criterion which draws a line in the $\sigma - \tau$ space (Fig. 3-2) and is expressed mathematically as:

$$\tau = \sigma \tan(\varphi) + b$$

where the model parameters φ and b are the parameters of the rock namely angle of internal friction and cohesion respectively. We will in this report shift between mathematical spaces that describe mechanical stability. We will use $\tau\sigma$ -space, s_1s_3 -space and qp -space to report the limits of mechanical stability.

Fig. 3-2: Mohr-Coulomb failure envelope.

3.2 2D vs 3D assessment

A 2D assessment, by considering only the least and largest principal stresses (s_3 and s_1) were made. The intermediate stress (s_2) were omitted from the analysis. In a typical reservoir Earth system, the largest principal stress is vertical, and the thus the two other principal stresses are horizontal. In a cylindrical case, as employed in all geomechanical tests in this work, the axial stress is s_1 and the two horizontal stresses are in the θ and radial direction, where the latter are equal $s_2 = s_3$. When omitting the intermediate stress from the failure geomechanical assessment to reservoir systems, the mathematics is simplified, and if the safe region is identified in the 2D-case then it is surely safe in 3D. This argument is based on experiments performed on true, polyaxial stress tests that display a stronger material strength than cylindrical cases (see page 274-275 in Fjær et al. 2008).

$s_2 = s_3$ is equivalent to the 2D assessment, while if $s_2 > s_3$ the intermediate compressive stress will reduce the likelihood that shear failure will occur because the side horizontal stress holds the rock volume together (due to friction and material continuity). Here, we make a conservative analysis by assuming $s_1 > s_2 = s_3$, thus if s_2 were higher than s_3 , it would carry more of the external load. If the analysis displays stability in 2D, it will be stable also in a 3D setting. In conclusion if we from a 2D geomechanical assessment can ensure stability, the area of the 'safe region' is under-estimated (i.e. the unsafe region is overestimated in size). The assessment is conservative.

Further on, we have no knowledge of what the Earth stresses in the Zar3-field is, thus a more complicated 3D analysis would not add credibility to our study.

3.3 Effective stress and tensile failure from $\tau\sigma$ to qp space

In field, the effective stress along principal direction i is described via $s'_i = s_i - \alpha_B P_f$, where s_i is the tectonic (external) stress in the principal direction $i = 1,2,3$, α_B is the Biot coefficient and P_f is the pore pressure (acting opposite direction as the imposed stress and thus, from the sign convention in geomechanics is given with a minus sign). The pore pressure, therefore, carry some of the imposed load and when the pore pressure is depleted this leads to increased compressive stress on the porous body.

Here the mathematical basis for transferring failure data from $\tau\sigma$ space to qp space is described. The basic premise is that a tensile crack criterion will grow in a plane with its surface normal parallel to the lowest principal stress direction. Using the effective stress relation, tensile fracture grow when pore pressure exceeds $P_f \geq \frac{T_0 + s_3}{\alpha_B}$.

If pre-existing cracks exist, with a surface normal parallel to s_3 , then these re-open when $P_f \geq \frac{s_3}{\alpha_B}$.

The qp -space is defined via:

$$q = s_1 - s_3$$

$$p = \frac{s_1 + s_3}{2} - \alpha_B P_f$$

Re-shuffling tensile crack criterion, $s_3 = -T_0 + \alpha_B P_f$. If this criterion is displayed in qp -space, then

$$q = s_1 + T_0 - \alpha_B P_f$$

$$p = \frac{1}{2}(s_1 - T_0 - \alpha_B P_f)$$

This criterion is represented in qp -space both with with measurements of T_0 and pre-existing fractures i.e. $T_0 = 0$.

3.4 Shear failure from $\tau\sigma$ to pq space

Here we combine $s_1 s_3$, $\tau\sigma$ to determine how the shear failure line is expressed in the pq -space.

Unconfined compressive and triaxial strength (UCS and 3ax) test of cylindrical samples was performed by axial loading s_1 until failure occur with $s_3 = 0$ and $s_3 = 7\text{MPa}$ for UCS and 3-axial, respectively as displayed in $s'_1 s'_3$ -plots (Fig. 3-3).

Fig. 3-3: Example of s₁ and s₃ plot of UCS (left dot) and 3-axial test (right). The slope is extracted.

The intercept with y-axis is C_0 and the slope is given as $\tan^2 \beta$. In $s'_1 s'_3$ -space shear failure occurs when the axial stress exceeds the line. Typically, for all frictional materials s_1 increases with increasing s'_3 . The envelope is expressed via,

$$s'_1 = s_1 - \alpha_B P_f = C_0 + \tan^2 \beta (s_3 - \alpha_B P_f)$$

Re-shuffle and solve for s_3 yields,

$$s_3 = \frac{1}{\tan^2 \beta} (s_1 - \alpha_B P_f - C_0) + \alpha_B P_f$$

Using this in qp yields the two expressions,

$$q = s_1 - \frac{1}{\tan^2 \beta} (s_1 - \alpha_B P_f - C_0) + \alpha_B P_f$$

$$p = \frac{1}{2} (s_1 - \alpha_B P_f) + \frac{1}{\tan^2 \beta} (s_1 - \alpha_B P_f - C_0)$$

The advantage of using qp -space is whilst the failure envelope can be given, each reservoir stress is given as a single dot (not a circle as in $\tau\sigma$ -space. We assume the intermediate stress is equal to the lowest principal stress, so that the value of q is maximized, and p is minimized, bringing each realization closer to the failure line. This is also a conservative choice enabling credibility to our results.

The shear strength, tensile strength (of a reservoir rock), and tensile strength of already fractured rocks with its surface normal parallel to s_3 are displayed in Fig. 3-4.

Fig. 3-4: Shear failure and tensile failure in qp -diagram.

4 EXPERIMENTAL METHODS DESCRIPTION - STRENGTHS AND STIFFNESS

This chapter describes the methods used in the determination of the geomechanical parameters.

4.1 Rock handling

MND had rock samples in their core storage facility in Lužice. In collaboration with WP5 and WP1, rock core samples were split between the work packages. In WP4, cylindrical test specimens/core plugs were drilled out of the cores with a prescribed diameter and length. In all 19 large cores were acquired from MND, that enabled us to make 63 core plugs /test specimens for mechanical testing, some of which was used in the reaction cabinet for CO₂ exposure. Sound velocity measurements were performed on all samples, and only a limited number had a shape that made them appropriate for confining pressure cycle measurements, triaxial (3Ax) tests and unconfined compressive tests (UCS and Brazilian tests of tensile strength.

4.2 Mechanical strength test methods

Here, we describe the methods used to determine the rock strengths.

4.2.1 Triaxial test

In triaxial tests cylindrical samples are held at a constant radial stress while continuously loaded axially until the rock fails where the principal stresses are noted. During loading the dynamic elastic Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio is obtained. In cylindrical geometries, the axial stress (σ_{ax}) is larger than the radial and angular (σ_r and σ_θ) stresses that are the same. These three represent the principal stresses. For this reason, we only report the axial and radial stresses. This text we refer to multiple variations of the same, where $\sigma_1 = \sigma_{ax} = s_1$ and $\sigma_3 = \sigma_r = s_3$.

The triaxial test usually starts with hydrostatic compression of a specimen ($\sigma_{ax} = \sigma_r$) to a prescribed confining pressure level. The confining pressure usually represents the horizontal stresses in the rock environment, but 7 MPa is used here. After that the confining pressure (i.e. radial stress σ_r) is kept constant while the axial stress increases.

For multiple rock specimens at we combine the triaxial tests with unconfined tests, where $\sigma_r = 0$ MPa. By plotting the failure stress states for the pair of UCS and 3-axial tests Mohr-Coulomb failure envelope, in $\sigma - \tau$ space, can be obtained by the tangent of the two Mohr's circles.

This relationship can take a form of a K_f line in a $p - q$ space which is computationally more easier to calculate as it doesn't envelope the circle but rather goes through a point in the middle of the circle (Fig. 4-1) which has coordinates,

$$(p, q) = \left(\frac{1}{2}(\sigma_1 + \sigma_3), \frac{1}{2}(\sigma_1 - \sigma_3) \right)$$

Its model parameters ψ and a have following relationship to the Mohr-Coulomb's ϕ and c as:

$$\phi = \sin^{-1}(\tan(\psi))$$

$$b = \frac{a}{\cos(\phi)}$$

Fig. 4-1: Relationship between K_f and M-C failure criterion.

Using this approach allows us to estimate the shear strength of a rock specimen at specific stress conditions by exploiting the property of Mohr's diagram to transform the stress tensor basis with respect to principal stress directions. Constructing such an envelope allows us to evaluate a stress state in the rock environment as being either in the region of stability or failure within the $\sigma - \tau$ space for a particular rock.

The Department of Mining Engineering and Safety under the Faculty of Mining and Geology at VSB-Technical University of Ostrava (VSB) is equipped with the Controls triaxial loading frame with a Hoek triaxial cells that require a cylindrical sample with 50 mm diameter and of a 100 mm length. The department was also recently equipped with a Hoek cell for a cylindrical sample with 38 mm diameter and 75 mm length.

4.2.2 Unconfined compressive strength test

To further enhance the information about a sample, i.e. to populate the Mohr's diagram with additional data, an unconfined compressive strength test is performed. In this case a test specimen is loaded only in its axial direction while the confining pressure is not applied at all. A rock specimen is being loaded with progressively larger axial stress magnitude until its failure. A maximal stress achieved during this type of experiment is the unconfined compressive strength (UCS) of the rock. This type of test produces a Mohr's circle that starts in the origin as $\sigma_2 = \sigma_3 = 0$.

The geomechanical test lab at VSB is equipped with the MTS 816 Rock Test System press that allows the evaluation of this material property.

4.2.3 Brazilian test

To evaluate tensile strength TS of the rock specimen the direct tensile strength test is seldom employed. Brazilian test determines indirectly the tensile strength of the rock by splitting it by compression. Test specimens for this type of test are in a shape of a tablet with length l being half of their diameter D . As long as the shape and quality of the test specimen are sufficient the theory of elasticity can be used to calculate the tensile stress caused by a compressive load on the side surface of the specimen as:

$$T_0 = 0.636 \frac{\sigma_1}{DL}$$

Fig. 4-2: Brazilian test set-up.

The geomechanical lab at VSB is equipped with the MTS 816 Rock Test System hydraulic press with special jaws (Fig. 4-2) so it can be used to perform the Brazilian test.

4.3 Static mechanical stiffness tests

Stiffness of a rock is a measure of the rock's response to loading in the form of deformation (Fig. 4-3). Stiff rocks respond to a load with small deformation relative to a rock which is less stiff under the same load. The deformation is a change in a configuration of geometry of a sample, i.e. a change of shape and volume, expressed as strain ε . The deformational compliance to a load can be quantified by a material constant, e.g. an elastic modulus, which is a proportionality constant between a loading force and the response deformation. Elastic moduli are dependent on amplitude of strain and frequency with which the load is applied or the rate at which the corresponding strain changes, i.e. the strain rate.

Fig. 4-3: Stress-strain relationship.

4.3.1 Static stiffness

In the case of the static loading the load is increasing at a low rate while the dimensions of the rock specimen are measured and static elastic modulus of a rock can be calculated.

For example the axial stress and the axial strain measured during an UCS test can be related by a constant E called the Young's modulus in the linear elastic deformation regime:

$$E = \frac{\partial \sigma_a}{\partial \varepsilon_a}$$

which measures the stiffness of a rock when a load is applied axially. The sample however doesn't change just in the axial direction but rather deforms in other directions as well (Fig. 4-4:).

Fig. 4-4: Thinning of a material in y z plane as it is being stretched in the x direction.

Only axial deformation cannot capture the whole deformation process on its own. In order to describe the deformation of a rock we employ another constant that describes deformation in the other directions, in this case of UCS compression it is the Poisson's ratio ν that relates radial and axial strains at corresponding load as:

$$\nu = -\frac{\varepsilon_r}{\varepsilon_a}$$

With the knowledge of two elastic moduli of a rock, other elastic moduli can be calculated, e.g. the bulk modulus K relating hydrostatic pressure to volumetric strain:

$$K = \frac{E}{3(1 - 2\nu)}$$

These quantities are a result of measurement of the deformation of a specimen during UCS or triaxial tests using dilatometers and tensiometers on the sample.

4.3.2 Dynamic stiffness from sound velocity

Dynamic loading takes form of a high frequency vibration applied on one face of a test specimen and registered on the other end. This type of deformation reaches strain amplitudes that are usually multiple orders of magnitude lower than those registered during a static loading experiment. Knowing the density ρ , the dynamic elastic moduli of an isotropic material can be calculated using velocities of pressure and shear elastic waves (v_p and v_s) via:

$$E_{dyn} = \rho v_s^2 \frac{3v_p^2 - 4v_s^2}{v_p^2 - v_s^2}$$

$$\nu_{dyn} = \frac{v_p^2 - 2v_s^2}{2(v_p^2 - 2v_s^2)}$$

Measurement of elastic wave velocities is done using the ultrasonic logger equipment UKS 14 (Geotron-Elektronik) from the project partner NORCE.

4.4 Pore volume compressibility

Porosity ϕ is a ratio of pore volume V_p and the bulk volume V_b of a rock:

$$\phi = \frac{V_p}{V_b}$$

The initial bulk volume of the cylindrical rock specimen was measured by a sliding caliper. The Faculty of Mining and Geology at VSB-Technical University of Ostrava is equipped with COREVAL 700 (Vinci Tech.) that measures open pore volume of a rock. It employs the Boyle's law for real gases to evaluate the pore volume. It performs the measurement while confining the sample with a hydrostatic (same in both axial and radial direction) pressure from 4 to 31.7 MPa for most samples, although two samples were loaded up to 45.5 MPa. The pressure of the N_2 were kept at 1.4 MPa, so that the corresponding peak hydrostatic effective stresses were 30.3 MPa and 44.1 MPa.

Thus, for each sample a relation between confining pressure, pore volume and Nitrogen Klinkenberg permeability is obtained. From $V_b = V_p + V_r$, where V_r is the volume of the rock volume (from Quant Rietveld method see later section), the volume of the rock is estimated. This is used to assess rock compressibility as function of porosity. The repeatability is evaluated to assess if permanent rock damage occurs when the confining effective stress is loaded and unloaded. This is used to determine hydrostatic stress at which compaction failure may occur, or equivalently, the 'safe region' in which compaction failure will not occur. If permanent damage occurred during loading, the unloading cycle will follow a different path in stress-strain diagrams.

4.4.1 Compressibility upon confining pressure compaction

A drained porous rock under an external load will compact. The resulting deformation is a product of a change in pore volume and the change of the volume of the mineral frame of the rock. Measuring a series of pore volumes of the rock with increasing load magnitude

allows to express relationship between pore volume and confining pressure P_c with the compressibility c_{pc} :

$$c_{pc} = -\frac{1}{V_p} \frac{\partial V_p}{\partial P_c}$$

where the notation of Zimmerman (1991) is used. The first subscript denotes the volume that is being deformed by a load, i.e. p for the pore volume and b for bulk volume. The second letter in the subscript denotes the type of load being imposed on the sample and causing the volumetric deformation, i.e. p for pore pressure changes and c confining pressure changes. Relationship between compressibilities is:

$$c_{bc} = c_m + \phi c_{pc}$$

where c_m is compressibility of the rock matrix, or in other words the mineral frame of the rock. Compressibility of the rock matrix is calculated as a reciprocal value of rock matrix bulk modulus (K_m). The rock matrix bulk modulus is calculated as a weighted average of bulk moduli of individual minerals (K_i) with the weights (w_i) being the percentages of the mineral content in the rock, calculated as:

$$\frac{1}{c_m} = K_m = \sum_{i=1}^n K_i w_i$$

Bulk moduli of individual minerals are reported in Fjær et al. (2008). Fraction of individual minerals in the rock are reported by CGS in the “*Quant Rietveld*” tab of the database. By calculating bulk compressibility of the rock using the expression above, we can calculate the bulk volume of the rock specimen investigated in 3.4 and calculate its porosity. The bulk volume is estimated with:

$$V_b(P_c) = V_b(0)e^{-c_{bc}P_c}$$

Calculated bulk volume is then used together with measured pore volume in calculation of porosity. Porosity is calculated as a function of confining pressure $\phi(P_c)$ and reported for the confining pressure value of $P_c = 18 \text{ MPa}$ in the “*MasterOverview*” tab of the database.

4.5 Thermo-elasticity

To quantify a deformation of a rock as a response to temperature change, the thermal expansion coefficient a is measured. In this case the volumetric strain ε_v depends on the temperature T and a relationship between volume a temperature is proportional to:

$$a_T = \frac{1}{V_b} \frac{\partial V_b}{\partial T} = \frac{\partial \varepsilon_v}{\partial T}$$

The Department of Mining Engineering and Safety under the Faculty of Mining and Geology at VSB-Technical University of Ostrava performs this measurement using an oven and measuring the corresponding deformation with a micro-meter measuring device. Due to technical reasons only the axial strain ε_a was measured. Considering the thermal expansion to be uniform the volumetric strain will be calculated as

$$\varepsilon_v = 3\varepsilon_a$$

Specimens were tempered in an airconditioned laboratory to 22 °C and their length was measured before heated in an oven to 100 °C for 24 hours and then their length was measured again. The data was then used to calculate the thermal expansion coefficient α_T .

4.6 Poroelastic parameters

Once a fluid is introduced into the pore space of the rock, the pore fluid pressure (P_f) counteracts the stress in the frame of the rock. The resulting effective stress can be calculated as:

$$\sigma' = \sigma - \alpha_B P_f$$

where α_B is the Biot's coefficient. Biot's coefficient is calculated as:

$$\alpha = 1 - \frac{K}{K_r}$$

where K is the bulk modulus of the rock and K_r is the bulk modulus of the rock matrix of the rock.

4.7 Using Quant Rietveld datasheet

We use data provided by CGS, collected in WP5 to calculate stiffness of the rock matrix by weighting bulk moduli of individual minerals (as reported in the literature – included in the row 2 of the sheet) by their fractional content in the mineral composition of the rock (see 3.4.1 Compressibility). This is done to estimate the volume of the rock as function of confining pressure in the COREVAL 700 confining pressure cycles.

The calculation is performed on the data in columns AC and AD in the 'Quant Rietveld' sheet in the WP4 data base. The rock matrix compressibility was used in estimation of Biot's coefficient (3.6). Average for Vranovice carbonates formation is then calculated in the cell AD41 and used as c_r value as their variance is in the order of 10^{-15} .

4.8 Heat capacity and thermal conductivity

The thermal parameters of the rocks were measured using the Izomet 2104 device. The measurement was performed with an attachment probe on the faces of the delivered cylindrical samples. On each body, measurements were taken at three different places on the forehead. At each location, the measurement was repeated 5 times. The samples were used for measurements in the condition supplied by the customer, without drying or mechanical treatment of the sample.

5 RESULTS

The complete data base of results is given in the Excel spread sheet named ‘WP4-MASTER_Results_CO2SPICER.xls’. We go through the key data here.

5.1 Poro-Perm datasheet

This datasheet contains truncated data export from the ‘Poroperm software’ provided with the ‘COREVAL 700’ porosimeter and permeameter both developed by Vinci Technologies. Several lines are dedicated to one test specimen. The block of rows for individual specimens are separated by horizontal lines and merged ID cell in column K. Individual lines contain measured data for a specific confining pressure level.

This data sheet contains both original output from the porosimeter and permeameter as well as compressibility derived from the data (4.4.1) and corrected bulk volumes and porosities (highlighted in light green - see Fig. 5.1).

A	C	D	E	F	G	H	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V
N°	Pc (MPa)	Vp(cc)	Keff[n2](mD)	φ(%)	K _∞ (mD)	b[n2] (psi)	Name	Vb0(cc)	Vb(cc)	Vg(cc)	pg (g/cc)	pb (g/cc)	cpc (1/MPa)	cbp (1/MPa)	cbc (1/MPa)	cr	Vb_corr	φ_corr
0	18,1676926	2,0506	0,8902489	3,63728	0,57241	8,32882	ZA7c1b6b	56,707	56,3774	54,3268	2,85053	2,74685	2,542E-03	9,508E-05	1,076E-04	1,25358E-05	56,596	0,036
1	6,89476	2,114933	1,19722	3,73983	0,80288	7,36729			56,5516	54,4366	2,84478	2,73839					56,623	0,037
2	13,78952	2,07292	0,9709843	3,67309	0,63238	8,03156			56,4353	54,3623	2,84866	2,74403					56,554	0,036
3	18,1676926	2,051554	0,8970286	3,63898	0,57747	8,30058			56,3773	54,3257	2,85058	2,74685					56,596	0,036
4	25,0624526	2,012911	0,7959286	3,5749	0,50326	8,72309			56,3068	54,2939	2,85226	2,75029					56,554	0,036
5	31,9572126	1,979868	0,7190236	3,51945	0,44751	9,10058			56,255	54,2751	2,85324	2,75282					56,512	0,035
6	25,0624526	1,984074	0,7351771	3,52343	0,45915	9,0178			56,3108	54,3268	2,85053	2,75009					56,554	0,035
7	18,1676926	1,999162	0,7776488	3,54567	0,4899	8,81049			56,3832	54,384	2,84753	2,74656					56,596	0,035
8	6,89476	2,105703	1,172991	3,72348	0,78416	7,43782	56,552	54,4463	2,84427	2,73836	56,665	0,037						
9	4,136856	0,408783	0,07080856	0,71546	0,04834	6,97286	UH11c4b3b	57,1594	57,1356	56,7268	2,69643	2,67714	9,726E-03	6,959E-05	8,212E-05	57,140	0,007	
10	11,031616	0,38492	0,03355747	0,67405	0,02373	6,21109			57,1059	56,721	2,69671	2,67853				57,108	0,007	
11	17,926376	0,335873	0,01951288	0,58831	0,01997	5,95122			57,0913	56,7554	2,69507	2,67922				57,075	0,006	
12	24,821136	0,311067	0,01211288	0,54496	0,00838	6,67146	57,0811	56,77	2,69438	2,6797	57,043	0,005						
13	31,715896	0,308647	0,00774381	0,54082	0,00555	5,9161	57,0702	56,7616	2,69478	2,68021	57,011	0,005						
14	24,821136	0,311579	0,0082322	0,54585	0,00551	7,39468	57,0809	56,7693	2,69441	2,6797	57,043	0,005						
15	17,926376	0,313372	0,00904218	0,54885	0,00585	8,18367	57,0957	56,7823	2,6938	2,67901	57,075	0,005						
16	11,031616	0,340338	0,0113081	0,59592	0,00787	6,54781	57,1118	56,7715	2,69431	2,67825	57,108	0,006						
17	4,136856	0,388194	0,01846406	0,67941	0,01307	6,19174	57,1367	56,7485	2,6954	2,67709	57,140	0,007						
18	4,136856	2,265355	23,29591	3,80895	13,3132	7,35117	ZA4Ac3b3b	59,7209	59,6133	57,2412	2,6121	2,50817	1,123E-03	4,276E-05	5,529E-05	59,707	0,038	
19	11,031616	2,265355	19,8377599	3,80895	13,3132	7,35117			59,4745	57,2092	2,61357	2,51402				59,684	0,038	
20	17,926376	2,246923	18,7686781	3,78478	12,9918	6,7703			59,3674	57,1205	2,61762	2,51855				59,662	0,038	
21	24,821136	2,227332	17,8412729	3,75685	13,0064	5,57601	59,2872	57,0599	2,6204	2,52196	59,639	0,037						
22	31,715896	2,196703	17,1544282	3,70882	13,7492	3,71497	59,2291	57,0324	2,62167	2,52443	59,616	0,037						
23	24,821136	2,185366	17,4438031	3,68571	12,3678	6,15627	59,2929	57,1075	2,61822	2,52172	59,639	0,037						
24	17,926376	2,210179	17,7166021	3,72263	12,8077	5,7492	59,3714	57,1612	2,61576	2,51838	59,662	0,037						
25	11,031616	2,216557	18,1846047	3,72667	14,7897	3,44322	59,4782	57,2616	2,61117	2,51386	59,684	0,037						
26	4,136856	2,286786	20,4532627	3,83586	13,4261	7,85098	59,6159	57,3291	2,6081	2,50805	59,707	0,038						
27	4,136856	0,834646	0,25797838	1,44332	0,25467	0,19474	57,8282	56,9936	2,75873	2,71891	57,866	0,014						
28	11,031616	0,828899	0,20674193	1,43494	0,18667	1,61278	57,7656	56,9367	2,76149	2,72186	57,852	0,014						
29	17,926376	0,818314	0,18068567	1,41775	0,17886	0,58594	57,7187	56,9003	2,76375	2,72408	57,838	0,014						

Fig. 5-1: Snapshot of the Poro-Perm datasheet outline.

The data in the columns that are not highlighted are affected by the fact that the bulk volume (V_b) of the specimen is not known after its confinement in the core-holder. By estimating the bulk compressibility of the specimen due to confining pressure (c_{bc}) we can calculate the corrected bulk volume (V_{b_corr}) and then corrected porosity ϕ_{corr} . Both are reported respectively in columns ‘U’ and ‘V’ in the datasheet, and, column ‘W’ and ‘X’ dedicated to confining pressure and Klinkenberg permeability, respectively.

Appendix 8.7 and 8.5 presents the data in a truncated form where 21 measurements were done across 6 different lithologies present in the Zar-3 field. Fig. 5-2 shows number of samples representing individual lithostratigraphic units.

Fig. 5-2: Lithology representation in poro-perm tests.

5.2 Sound velocity determination

The WP4SmpOverview datasheet in the 'WP4-MASTER_Results_CO2SPICER.lx' excel spreadsheet submitted along this report contains dynamic stiffness data in columns AD:AG, and columns AV:AZ (for samples exposed to CO₂). The first two columns are v_p and v_s while the next two columns contain dynamic elastic moduli calculated (section 4.3.2). Appendix 7.5 presents the data in a truncated form. Overall, 73 measurements were done across 6 different lithologies present in the Zar-3 field. Fig. 5-3 shows number of samples representing individual lithostratigraphic units.

Fig. 5-3: Lithology representation in sound velocity tests

5.3 Tensile strength

In all, 23 Brazilian tests of tensile strength were performed and the experimental results are reported in appendix 7.3. The sample distribution among individual lithologies of the Zar-3 field is represented in Fig. 5-4.

Fig. 5-4: Lithology representation in tensile strength tests.

5.4 Triaxial strength determination

In total, four triaxial tests were performed and the experimental results are reported in appendix 7.1. The sample distribution among individual lithologies of the Zar-3 field is represented in Fig. 5-5.

Fig. 5-5: Lithology representation in triaxial strength tests.

5.5 Unconfined compressive strength (UCS)

The ‘UCS’ datasheet contains the experimental details and results. The way in which parameters were derived are described in Section 4.2.2. The main results are highlighted in light green in columns A, I, O, and Q. Additional details as a loading rate, laboratory temperature, etc. are included.

The test procedure follows standard protocol where the strain gauges are glued onto the specimen in axial direction and on its outer circumference. Specimen is then placed into the hydraulic press and loaded with a minimal load of 10 kN. Strain gauge is then reset to zero and the loading proceeds with a constant loading rate $1.1 \text{ kN}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. The loading then continues until the failure of the specimen. At that point the maximal load is recorded and reported as the unconfined compressive strength of the rock. Recorded axial and radial strains are processed as the function of load and elastic parameters of the rock are thus derived.

Samples ‘ZA3_c3_b1_a’ and ‘ZA4A_c3_b3_a’ were evaluated for their unconfined compressive strength however due to a technical failure (strain gauge short circuit) in one

case and the condition of the sample in the other, their static stiffness properties weren't evaluated.

In total, eight triaxial tests were performed and the experimental results are reported in appendix 8.2. The sample distribution among individual lithologies of the Zar-3 field is represented in Fig. 5-6.

Fig. 5-6: Lithology representation in UCS tests.

Static stiffness data are reported in the appendix 8.4.

5.6 Thermal expansion coefficient

Thermal expansion datasheet contains data on thermal expansion coefficient measurement, i.e. axial length of a specimen at 20 °C and at 100 °C. In total 4 measurements of thermoelastic properties were done and the experimental results are reported in Appendix 8.6. The sample distribution among individual lithologies of the Zar-3 field is represented in Fig. 5-7.

Fig. 5-7: Lithology representation in thermal expansion tests.

5.7 Failure envelopes

Failure envelopes of triaxial tests combined with UCS are provided here. Mohr-Coulomb failure parameters (Tab. 5-1), namely the coefficients of cohesion and internal friction were calculated using formulas presented in Section 4.2.1. The input qp data were obtained by testing two rock specimens, representing a lithological member of the Zar-3 field for their UCS and triaxial strength. The corresponding Mohr circles are shown in Figs. 5.8 - 5.10.

Table 5-1: Mohr-Coulomb parameters.

Friction	Cohesion	Sample ID	Lithostratigraphy	Type
-	MPa			
0.39	12.30	ZA4A_c1_b5_a	Vranovice Fm. (Upper Jurassic)	Reservoir
		ZA4A_c3_b3_b	Vranovice Fm. (Upper Jurassic)	Reservoir
1.15	28.44	UH11_c4_b3_a	Vranovice Fm. Kurdějov (Ernstbrunn Fm?)	Reservoir
		UH11_c4_b3_b	Vranovice Fm. Kurdějov (Ernstbrunn Fm?)	Reservoir
1.78	5.72	ZA3_c1_b1_b	Žarošice Mb.	Seal
		ZA3_c1_b1_c	Žarošice Mb.	Seal

Fig. 5-8: Mohr-Coulomb failure envelope representing mechanical stability of the Vranovice Fm.

Fig. 5-9: Mohr-Coulomb failure envelope representing mechanical stability of the Žarosice Member.

Fig. 5-10: Mohr-Coulomb failure envelope representing mechanical stability of the Vranovice Fm. and Kurdějov (Ernstbrunn?) Fm.

5.8 Thermal properties determination

The heat capacity and thermal conductivity were measured the Izomet 2104 device at VSB. In all, 27 samples were quantified. The Mikulov Fm. (marls) are sealing, while the Vranovice Fm. (dolomite) and the Kurdějov Fm. represent reservoir rock types. The results are displayed in Tab.5-2.

Tab. 5-2. Average values of heat capacity and thermal conductivity for three formations.

Lithology	Heat capacity	Thermal conductivity	#smpls
	$c_p \cdot 10^6$ (J/m ³ .K)	λ (W/m.K)	
Vranovice Fm.	2.00	2.92	21
Vranovice Fm. Kurdějov (Ernstbrunn Fm?)	2.08	2.77	3
Mikulov Marls	1.98	1.92	3

6 DATABASE DESCRIPTION

Data produced in the scope of WP4 are stored in an MS Excel spreadsheet on the project's repository. The spreadsheet contains main sheets:

- CORES+SAMPLING** overview of sampled cores from the MND repository with sampled intervals reported by CGS
- MasterOverview** contains information about rock specimens and data that the specimen provided

Additional sheets will be dedicated for fundamental experimental data as described above. The *MasterOverview* sheet dedicates one row of the sheet per specimen and contains one column per specimen property. Individual cells will then contain derived data (e.g. compressibility derived from porosity measurements, Mohr-Coulomb failure envelope parameters derived from a p-q diagrams).

6.1 List of cores and sampling – sample overview

This sheet was provided by MND and CGS partners in the CO₂-SPICER project. It contains data on core material from the core repository of MND. Its contents are well information (well name, well coordinates), core information (core no, box no, depth, lithology), core sample information (box interval, photo, interval mark on the box photograph), see Fig. 6-1.

	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O
1	Well	Depth	Depth	Depth	Depth	Cor	Bo	Recover	Stratigraphy	Lithostratigraphy	Type	Photography
100	ZA7	1940,00	1949,20	1636,00	1645,20	1	2	6,5	Upper Jurassic	Vranovice Dolomite	Reservoir	
101	ZA7	1940,00	1949,20	1636,00	1645,20	1	6	6,5	Upper Jurassic	Vranovice Dolomite	Reservoir	
102	ZA7	1940,00	1949,20	1636,00	1645,20	1	7	6,5	Upper Jurassic	Vranovice Dolomite	Reservoir	
103												
104												
105												
106												
107												
108												
109												
110												

Fig. 6-1: A snapshot of the CORES+SAMPLING sheet layout.

7 DISCUSSION – CORE SAMPLES SURVIVAL BIAS

Geology is variable at all scales. Core samples were acquired from the Zar-3 field and stored in the MND core repository. A series of drill cores were acquired from the different wells around the Zar-3 site and stored in 1 m long wooden boxes; a core is usually stored in more boxes. Only cores material of sufficient size, i.e. with fragments that survived the coring, handling and storage could be used for geomechanical assessment. Thus, we must emphasise that care must be taken when applying geomechanical stiffness and strength core sample results to the overall field property. Therefore, a so-called survival bias is expected to affect the applicability where samples that were strong enough to withstand the coring, extraction, handling, and storage were tested, and the corresponding weaker parts of the reservoir were, presumably, fractured and disintegrated – and thus were not tested.

To compensate for the above disclaimer, we have made conservative choices when combining strengths and field effective stress estimates in our analysis.

The result data base will be used in the other Work Packages and in the generation of the upcoming deliveries in the project.

REFERENCES

- Fjær, E., Holt, R. M., Horsrud, P., Raaen, A. M., Risnes, R. (2008): Petroleum related rock mechanics 2nd edition. Developments in petroleum science vol. 53, Elsevier Science Pub. Co., 491 pp, ISBN 978-0-444-50260-5.
- Zimmerman, R. W. (1991): Compressibility of sandstones. Developments in petroleum science vol. 29, Elsevier Science Pub. Co., 183 pp, ISBN 978-0444883254.

8 APPENDICES

Here we report tables of all Geomechanical parameters that may be found in the Excel document 'WP4-MASTER-Results_CO2SPICER.xls'.

8.1 Triaxial strength data

Sample ID	Type	Lithostratigraphy	Radial Stress	Axial strength at failure
			MPa	MPa
ZA3_c1_b1_c	Seal	Žarošice Mb.	7	145.98
ZA4A_c3_b3_b	Reservoir	Vranovice Fm.	7	51
UH11_c4_b3_b	Reservoir	Vranovice Fm. Kurdějov (Ernstbrunn Fm?)	7	202
ZA7_c1_b6_b	Reservoir	Vranovice Fm.	15	165.93

8.2 Unconfined compressive strength (UCS) data

Sample ID	Type	Lithostratigraphy	Axial strength at failure
			MPa
ZA3_c3_b1_a	Reservoir	Vranovice Fm.	55.2
ZA4A_c3_b3_a	Reservoir	Vranovice Fm.	3.1
ZA6A_c1_b4_a	Reservoir	Vranovice Fm.	62.0
ZA4A_c1_b5_a	Reservoir	Vranovice Fm.	36
UH11_c4_b3_a	Reservoir	Vranovice Fm. Kurdějov (Ernstbrunn Fm?)	152
ZA3_c1_b1_b	Seal	Žarošice Mb.	44
KOE6_c10_b2_a	Seal	Myslejovice Fm.	76.9
MIL1_c1_b1_a	Seal	Mikulov Fm.	49.8

8.3 Tensile strength data

Sample ID	Tensile strength	Lithostratigraphy;	Type	Average T0
	MPa			MPa
ZA7_c1_b2_a	3.09	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	3.31
ZA7_c1_b2_b	4.25			
ZA7_c1_b2_c	2.58			
ZA7_c1_b5_a	5.82	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	4.76
ZA7_c1_b5_b	4.58			
ZA7_c1_b5_c	3.89			
ZA7_c1_b6_a	1.96	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	1.96
ZA4A_c1_b3_a	2.55	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	2.14
ZA4A_c1_b3_b	1.905			
ZA4A_c1_b3_c	1.97			
UH11_c4_b3_d	6.4	Vranovice Fm. Kurdějov (Ernstbrunn Fm?)	Reservoir	6.97
UH11_c4_b3_c	7.54			
UH3_c4_b6_a	9.14	Mikulov Fm.	Seal	9.14
ZA3_c1_b1_a	3.9	Žarošice Mb.	Seal	6.18
ZA3_c1_b1_f	3.7			
ZA3_c1_b1_d	9.9			
ZA3_c1_b1_c	7.2			
KOE6_c10_b2_c	5.1	Myslejovice Fm.	Seal	4.15
KOE6_c10_b2_d	3.4			
KOE6_c10_b2_e	4			
KOE6_c10_b2_f	4.1			
MIL1_c1_b1_c	8.4	Mikulov Fm.	Seal	7.7
MIL1_c1_b1_d	7			

8.4 Static stiffness data

Sample ID	Lithostratigraphy	Type	v_stat	E_stat
			(-)	GPa
ZA4A_c1_b5_a	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	0.48	31.40
ZA6A_c1_b4_a	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	0.21	27.80

8.5 Dynamic stiffness data

Sample ID	Lithostratigraphy	Type	vp	vs	v_dyn	E_dyn
			km/s	km/s	GPa	GPa
UH11_c4_b3_a	Vranovice Fm. Kurdějov (Ernstbrunn Fm?)	Reservoir	5.13	2.63	0.32	49.44
UH11_c4_b3_b	Vranovice Fm. Kurdějov (Ernstbrunn Fm?)	Reservoir	6.01	3.09	0.32	68.19
UH11_c4_b3_c	Vranovice Fm. Kurdějov (Ernstbrunn Fm?)	Reservoir	7.00	3.59	0.32	89.76
UH11_c4_b3_Core	Vranovice Fm. Kurdějov (Ernstbrunn Fm?)	Reservoir	5.74	2.49	0.38	45.45
ZA3_c3_b1_a	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	4.75	2.59	0.29	46.87
ZA3_c3_b1_b	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	3.35	1.68	0.33	20.51
ZA3_c3_b1_c	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	5.83	2.35	0.40	41.06
ZA3_c3_b1_Core	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	4.62	1.52	0.44	18.07
ZA3_c3_b1_d	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	4.92	2.60	0.31	47.41
ZA3_c3_b3_Core	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	4.34	1.69	0.41	22.25
ZA4A_c1_b1_a	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	6.37	3.47	0.29	82.67
ZA4A_c1_b1_Core	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	4.38	1.80	0.40	23.86
ZA4A_c1_b3_a	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	5.78	2.49	0.39	45.17
ZA4A_c1_b3_b	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	8.29	3.91	0.36	104.16
ZA4A_c1_b3_c	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	4.67	2.01	0.39	29.14
ZA4A_c1_b3_Core	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	3.39	1.92	0.27	23.48
ZA4A_c1_b3_d	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	3.95	1.85	0.36	20.76
ZA4A_c1_b5_a	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	5.31	1.71	0.44	22.61
ZA4A_c1_b5_b	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	5.79	2.76	0.35	54.78
ZA4A_c1_b5_Core	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	4.26	1.38	0.44	14.25
ZA4A_c2_b5_a	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	3.58	1.74	0.35	20.93
ZA4A_c2_b5_Core	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	3.10	1.38	0.38	14.21
ZA4A_c3_b3_a	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	2.72	1.19	0.38	9.77
ZA4A_c3_b3_b	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	2.84	1.24	0.38	10.50
ZA4A_c3_b3_Core	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	2.02	1.29	0.16	9.89

Sample ID	Lithostratigraphy	Type	vp	vs	v_dyn	E_dyn
			km/s	km/s	GPa	GPa
ZA4A_c4_b2_a	Vranovice Fm. (Nikolčice Fm.)	Reservoir	2.43	1.51	0.18	13.16
ZA4A_c4_b2_Core	Vranovice Fm. (Nikolčice Fm.)	Reservoir	3.16	1.77	0.27	19.11
ZA6A_c1_b1_Core	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	4.05	2.19	0.29	28.95
ZA6A_c1_b2_a	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	4.52	2.22	0.34	33.76
ZA6A_c1_b2_Core	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	4.47	2.40	0.30	37.06
ZA6A_c1_b4_a	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	4.83	1.64	0.44	20.72
ZA6A_c1_b4_b	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	4.39	1.91	0.38	27.11
ZA6A_c1_b4_Core	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	4.45	2.06	0.36	28.94
ZA7_c1_b2_a	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	4.53	1.84	0.40	25.53
ZA7_c1_b2_b	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	4.65	1.87	0.40	26.21
ZA7_c1_b2_c	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	4.02	1.96	0.34	27.25
ZA7_c1_b2_Core	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	4.04	1.91	0.36	26.00
ZA7_c1_b5_a	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	3.94	1.80	0.37	23.83
ZA7_c1_b5_b	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	5.23	2.27	0.38	37.78
ZA7_c1_b5_c	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	5.04	2.68	0.30	48.74
ZA7_c1_b5_Core	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	4.93	2.50	0.33	44.62
ZA7_c1_b6_a	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	5.41	2.38	0.38	39.40
ZA7_c1_b6_b	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	4.64	2.14	0.37	33.99
ZA7_c1_b6_Core	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	3.80	1.66	0.38	20.00
UH3_c4_b6_Core	Mikulov Fm.	Seal	3.34	1.42	0.39	14.08
UH3_c4_b6_a	Mikulov Fm.	Seal	5.20	2.43	0.36	43.71
UH11_c4_b3_d	Vranovice Fm. Kurdějov (Ernstbrunn Fm?)	Reservoir	6.67	2.28	0.43	32.71
ZA3_c1_b3_a	Žarošice Mb.	Seal	5.68	3.31	0.24	59.83
ZA6A_c1_b4_c	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	4.79	2.45	0.32	41.22
ZA4A_c3_b3_c	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	2.11	0.82	0.41	4.93
ZA4A_c4_b2_b	Vranovice Fm. (Nikolčice Fm.)	Reservoir	3.14	1.64	0.31	17.70

Sample ID	Lithostratigraphy	Type	vp	vs	v_dyn	E_dyn
			km/s	km/s	GPa	GPa
ZA3_c1_b1_b	Žarošice Mb.	Seal	4.35	3.00	0.05	48.18
ZA3_c1_b1_c	Žarošice Mb.	Seal	5.60	3.07	0.29	61.65
ZA3_c1_b1_a	Žarošice Mb.	Seal	5.60	2.12	0.42	32.14
ZA3_c1_b1_d	Žarošice Mb.	Seal	6.66	3.38	0.33	80.42
ZA3_c1_b1_e	Žarošice Mb.	Seal	6.49	2.54	0.41	45.62
ZA3_c1_b1_f	Žarošice Mb.	Seal	6.47	3.19	0.34	66.70
ZA3_c1_b1_g	Žarošice Mb.	Seal	5.81	3.09	0.30	65.25
KOE6_c10_b2_a	Myslejovice Fm.	Seal	3.67	2.06	0.27	27.07
KOE6_c10_b2_b	Myslejovice Fm.	Seal	3.44	1.93	0.27	23.87
KOE6_c10_b2_c	Myslejovice Fm.	Seal	3.99	1.92	0.35	23.04
KOE6_c10_b2_d	Myslejovice Fm.	Seal	3.52	1.92	0.29	23.62
KOE6_c10_b2_e	Myslejovice Fm.	Seal	3.78	2.12	0.27	28.47
KOE6_c10_b2_f	Myslejovice Fm.	Seal	3.93	1.82	0.36	22.43
KOE6_c10_b2_g	Myslejovice Fm.	Seal	3.84	2.10	0.29	28.46
KOE6_c10_b2_h	Myslejovice Fm.	Seal	3.91	2.16	0.28	29.84
MIL1_c1_b1_a	Mikulov Fm.	Seal	4.54	2.49	0.29	40.27
MIL1_c1_b1_b	Mikulov Fm.	Seal	4.73	2.58	0.29	43.92
MIL1_c1_b1_c	Mikulov Fm.	Seal	5.53	2.68	0.35	49.48
MIL1_c1_b1_d	Mikulov Fm.	Seal	5.59	2.97	0.30	59.04
MIL1_c1_b1_e	Mikulov Fm.	Seal	5.13	3.05	0.23	58.65
MIL1_c1_b1_f	Mikulov Fm.	Seal	3.91	2.00	0.32	27.27
ZA6A_c1_b1_a	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	4.05	2.19	0.29	29.75

8.6 Thermal expansion data

Sample ID	α	Lithostratigraphy	Type
	K ⁻¹		
UH11_c4_b3_d	1.89E-03	Vranovice Fm. Kurdějov (Ernstbrunn Fm?)	Reservoir
UH3_c4_b6_a	6.48E-05	Mikulov Fm.	Seal
ZA4A_c1_b3_b	1.77E-05	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir
ZA4A_c1_b3_c	6.89E-05	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir

8.7 Poro-perm data

Sample ID	Pc (MPa)	ϕ (%)	K_{∞} (mD)	Litho	Type	cpc (1/MPa)	cbp (1/MPa)	cbc (1/MPa)
ZA7_c1_b6b	18.1677	0.036234	0.5724	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	2.62E-03	9.81E-05	1.11E-04
	6.8948	0.037324	0.8029					
	13.7895	0.036611	0.6324					
	18.1677	0.036251	0.5775					
	25.0625	0.035595	0.5033					
	31.9572	0.035038	0.4475					
	25.0625	0.035085	0.4591					
	18.1677	0.035325	0.4899					
6.8948	0.037161	0.7842						
UH11_c4_b3b	4.1369	0.007	0.0483	Vranovice Fm. Kurdějov (Ernstbrunn Fm?)	Reservoir	9.73E-03	6.96E-05	8.21E-05
	11.0316	0.007	0.0237					
	17.9264	0.006	0.0140					
	24.8211	0.005	0.0084					
	31.7159	0.005	0.0056					
	24.8211	0.005	0.0055					
	17.9264	0.005	0.0059					
	11.0316	0.006	0.0079					
4.1369	0.007	0.0131						
ZA4A_c3_b3b	4.1369	0.038	13.3132	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	1.12E-03	4.28E-05	5.53E-05
	11.0316	0.038	13.3132					
	17.9264	0.038	12.9318					
	24.8211	0.037	13.0064					
	31.7159	0.037	13.7492					
	24.8211	0.037	12.3678					
	17.9264	0.037	12.8077					
	11.0316	0.037	14.7897					
4.1369	0.038	13.4261						
ZA3_c3_b1a	4.1369	0.014	0.2547	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	1.52E-03	2.20E-05	3.45E-05
	11.0316	0.014	0.1867					
	17.9264	0.014	0.1739					
	24.8211	0.014	0.1602					
	31.7159	0.014	0.1412					
	24.8211	0.014	0.1347					
	17.9264	0.014	0.1482					
	11.0316	0.014	0.1730					
4.1369	0.015	0.2105						

Sample ID	Pc (MPa)	ϕ (%)	K_{∞} (mD)	Litho	Type	cpc (1/MPa)	cbp (1/MPa)	cbc (1/MPa)
UH11_c4_b3a	4.1369	0.004	0.0012	Vranovice Fm. Kurdějov (Ernstbrunn Fm?)	Reservoir	1.24E-02	5.55E-05	6.80E-05
	11.0316	0.004	0.0006					
	17.9264	0.003	0.0004					
	24.8211	0.003	0.0003					
	31.7159	0.003	0.0002					
ZA4A_c3_b3a	4.1369	0.038	8.1940	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	3.34E-03	1.27E-04	1.39E-04
	11.0316	0.037	7.1300					
	17.9264	0.035	6.6423					
	24.8211	0.035	6.4806					
	31.7159	0.035	6.0679					
	24.8211	0.034	6.1185					
	17.9264	0.034	6.3515					
	11.0316	0.035	6.7887					
ZA3_c3_b1b	4.1369	0.017	2.4950	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	2.88E-03	4.86E-05	6.11E-05
	11.0316	0.016	1.7465					
	17.9264	0.016	1.4095					
	24.8211	0.016	1.1317					
	31.7159	0.015	1.0401					
ZA6A_c1_b4a	4.1369	0.018	2.6915	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	4.81E-03	8.50E-05	9.75E-05
	11.0316	0.017	2.2416					
	17.9264	0.016	1.4967					
	24.8211	0.016	1.3858					
	31.7159	0.015	1.3029					
	24.8211	0.015	1.4386					
	17.9264	0.016	1.2657					
	11.0316	0.016	1.3961					
UH3_c4_b6a	4.1369	0.016	0.0014	Mikulov Fm.	Seal	7.34E-03	1.15E-04	1.27E-04
	11.0316	0.015	0.0003					
	17.9264	0.013	0.0001					
	24.8211	0.013	0.0001					
	31.7159	0.013	3.95E-05					
ZA4A_c1_b5a	4.1369	0.015	3.0636	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	6.11E-03	9.13E-05	1.04E-04
	11.0316	0.014	1.1680					
	17.9264	0.013	0.9317					
	24.8211	0.013	1.8103					
	31.7159	0.012	0.9404					
ZA4A_c2_b5a	4.1369	0.029	28.1940	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	6.99E-03	2.05E-04	2.17E-04
	11.0316	0.027	26.9862					

Sample ID	Pc (MPa)	ϕ (%)	K_{∞} (mD)	Litho	Type	cpc (1/MPa)	cbp (1/MPa)	cbc (1/MPa)
	17.9264	0.025	21.5589					
	24.8211	0.024	17.7909					
	31.7159	0.024	14.1017					
ZA4A_c1_b5b	4.1369	0.019	17.9035	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	4.30E-03	8.17E-05	9.42E-05
	11.0316	0.018	16.8261					
	17.9264	0.017	17.7324					
	24.8211	0.017	16.2062					
	31.7159	0.017	15.6561					
ZA4A_c1_b1a	4.1369	0.010	0.0136	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	1.50E-02	1.51E-04	1.63E-04
	11.0316	0.009	0.0071					
	17.9264	0.007	0.0050					
	24.8211	0.007	0.0041					
	31.7159	0.006	0.0034					
ZA4A_c4_b2a	4.1369	0.046	4.2142	Vranovice Fm. (Nikolčice Fm.)	Reservoir	2.61E-03	1.21E-04	1.34E-04
	11.0316	0.045	3.7420					
	17.9264	0.044	3.4865					
	24.8211	0.043	3.3926					
	31.7159	0.043	3.2356					
ZA6A_c1_b2a	4.1369	0.029	1.7721	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	2.16E-03	6.29E-05	7.55E-05
	11.0316	0.028	1.3627					
	17.9264	0.028	1.2224					
	24.8211	0.027	1.1248					
	31.7159	0.027	1.1679					
ZA3_c1_b1b	4.1369	0.018	0.0840888	Žarošice Mb.	Seal	4.67E-03	8.41E-05	9.66E-05
	11.0316	0.017	0.0692191					
	17.9264	0.016	0.0640938					
	24.8211	0.016	0.0629673					
	31.7159	0.016	0.0612041					
ZA3_c1_b1c	4.1369	0.058	0.039413	Žarošice Mb.	Seal	6.44E-03	3.73E-04	3.86E-04
	11.0316	0.053	0.0178466					
	17.9264	0.051	0.0138655					
	24.8211	0.049	0.0112425					
	31.7159	0.048	0.0103563					
ZA6A_c1_b1a	4.1369	0.107	19.43324	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	1.65E-03	1.77E-04	1.89E-04
	11.0316	0.104	20.06722					
	17.9264	0.101	19.69483					
	24.8211	0.101	17.95141					
	31.7159	0.101	18.23485					

Sample ID	Pc (MPa)	ϕ (%)	K_{∞} (mD)	Litho	Type	cpc (1/MPa)	cbp (1/MPa)	cbc (1/MPa)
	38.6107	0.100	18.63951					
	45.5054	0.100	18.57396					
	31.7159	0.100	18.70351					
	17.9264	0.100	18.47367					
	4.1369	0.104	20.48275					
ZA6A_c1_b2a	4.1369	0.061	5.598539	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	1.43E-03	8.77E-05	1.00E-04
	17.9264	0.059	3.77405					
	24.8211	0.058	3.312886					
	31.7159	0.058	3.446539					
	38.6107	0.058	3.094137					
	45.5054	0.058	3.113917					
	31.7159	0.058	3.187684					
	17.9264	0.059	3.287064					
4.1369	0.060	6.425254						
KOE6_c10_b2a	4.1369	0.041	0.058758	Myslejovice Fm.	Seal	4.95E-03	2.01E-04	2.13E-04
	11.0316	0.038	0.022122					
	17.9264	0.036	0.01115					
	24.8211	0.035	0.007975					
	31.7159	0.034	0.004219					
	38.6107	0.033	0.002868					
	45.5054	0.032	0.002165					
	31.7159	0.033	0.002968					
	17.9264	0.033	0.006272					
	4.1369	0.038	0.029779					
MIL1_c1_b1b	4.1369	0.046	0.200861	Mikulov Fm.	Seal	1.26E-02	5.80E-04	5.92E-04
	17.9264	0.035	0.137716					
	31.7159	0.027	0.085743					
	45.5054	0.023	0.043945					
	31.7159	0.023	0.045114					
	17.9264	0.024	0.066174					
4.1369	0.032	0.093158						

8.8 Thermal properties data

Sample ID	Lithostratigraphy	Type	Thermal conductivity	Average	Heat capacity	Average
			λ (W/m.K)	λ (W/m.K)	$c_p \cdot 10^6$ (J/m ³ .K)	$c_p \cdot 10^6$ (J/m ³ .K)
UH11_c4_b3	Vranovice Fm. Kurdějov (Ernstbrunn Fm?)	Reservoir	2.79	2.8	2.25	2.25
			2.8		2.26	
			2.79		2.25	
			2.8		2.25	
			2.81		2.25	
UH11_c4_b3	Vranovice Fm. Kurdějov (Ernstbrunn Fm?)	Reservoir	2.79	2.79	1.95	1.95
			2.79		1.95	
			2.79		1.95	
			2.79		1.95	
			2.79		1.95	
UH11_c4_b3	Vranovice Fm. Kurdějov (Ernstbrunn Fm?)	Reservoir	2.73	2.73	2.04	2.04
			2.72		2.04	
			2.73		2.04	
			2.73		2.04	
			2.74		2.03	
ZA3_c3_b1	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	3.7	3.7	2.23	2.23
			3.7		2.23	
			3.7		2.23	
			3.71		2.24	
			3.7		2.23	
ZA3_c3_b1	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	3.72	3.72	2.19	2.19
			3.72		2.19	
			3.72		2.19	
			3.73		2.19	
			3.71		2.18	
ZA3_c3_b1	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	3.7	3.69	2.22	2.21
			3.69		2.21	
			3.7		2.21	
			3.69		2.21	
			3.69		2.21	
ZA3_c3_b3	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	3.93	3.93	2.3	2.3
			3.92		2.3	
			3.93		2.3	
			3.94		2.3	
			3.94		2.29	

Sample ID	Lithostratigraphy	Type	Thermal conductivity	Average	Heat capacity	Average
			λ (W/m.K)	λ (W/m.K)	$c_p 10^6$ (J/m ³ .K)	$c_p 10^6$ (J/m ³ .K)
ZA3_c3_b3	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	3.46	3.47	2.24	2.24
			3.47		2.24	
			3.48		2.24	
			3.47		2.24	
			3.47		2.24	
ZA3_c3_b3	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	3.47	3.47	2.15	2.15
			3.46		2.15	
			3.47		2.15	
			3.47		2.15	
			3.46		2.14	
UH3_c4_b6	Mikulov Fm.	Seal	1.93	1.93	2	1.99
			1.93		2	
			1.93		2	
			1.93		1.99	
			1.94		1.98	
UH3_c4_b6	Mikulov Fm.	Seal	1.93	1.93	2.01	2.01
			1.93		2.01	
			1.93		2	
			1.94		2.01	
			1.93		2	
UH3_c4_b6	Mikulov Fm.	Seal	1.9	1.9	1.94	1.93
			1.9		1.94	
			1.9		1.94	
			1.91		1.93	
			1.9		1.92	
ZA4A_c1_b5	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	3.03	3.03	1.65	1.65
			3.02		1.65	
			3.02		1.66	
			3.03		1.65	
			3.03		1.64	
ZA4A_c1_b5	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	3.47	3.41	1.93	1.93
			3.39		1.93	
			3.38		1.93	
			3.38		1.93	
			3.42		1.91	
ZA4A_c1_b5	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	3.54	3.55	2.03	2.03
			3.55		2.03	
			3.54		2.03	
			3.55		2.03	
			3.58		2.02	

Sample ID	Lithostratigraphy	Type	Thermal conductivity	Average	Heat capacity	Average
			λ (W/m.K)	λ (W/m.K)	$c_p 10^6$ (J/m ³ .K)	$c_p 10^6$ (J/m ³ .K)
ZA4A_c2_b5	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	2.52	2.5	1.92	1.93
			2.49		1.94	
			2.49		1.94	
			2.49		1.94	
			2.49		1.93	
ZA4A_c2_b5	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	2.55	2.55	2.01	2.01
			2.55		2.01	
			2.55		2.01	
			2.56		2.01	
			2.56		2.01	
ZA4A_c2_b5	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	2.5	2.5	2.13	2.13
			2.49		2.14	
			2.5		2.14	
			2.5		2.13	
			2.51		2.13	
ZA4A_c1_b3	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	2.11	2.11	2	2.01
			2.11		2.01	
			2.11		2.01	
			2.11		2.01	
			2.11		2.01	
ZA4A_c1_b3	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	2.53	2.53	1.74	1.73
			2.53		1.73	
			2.53		1.73	
			2.54		1.73	
			2.52		1.71	
ZA4A_c1_b3	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	2.12	2.13	1.69	1.69
			2.13		1.69	
			2.13		1.69	
			2.14		1.69	
			2.11		1.68	
ZA4A_c1_b1	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	2.91	2.91	1.96	1.97
			2.92		1.98	
			2.9		1.98	
			2.9		1.98	
			2.9		1.96	
ZA4A_c1_b1	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	2.69	2.68	1.99	1.98
			2.69		1.98	
			2.66		1.97	
			2.7		1.98	
			2.68		1.96	

Sample ID	Lithostratigraphy	Type	Thermal conductivity	Average	Heat capacity	Average
			λ (W/m.K)	λ (W/m.K)	$c_p 10^6$ (J/m ³ .K)	$c_p 10^6$ (J/m ³ .K)
ZA4A_c1_b1	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	2.82	2.79	1.88	1.88
			2.76		1.88	
			2.78		1.88	
			2.84		1.88	
			2.74		1.86	
ZA4A_c3_b3	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	2.27	2.18	1.96	1.96
			2.15		1.96	
			2.14		1.96	
			2.14		1.96	
			2.2		1.96	
ZA4A_c3_b3	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	2.35	2.35	1.98	1.99
			2.35		1.99	
			2.35		1.99	
			2.35		1.99	
			2.35		1.98	
ZA4A_c3_b3	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	2.11	2.11	1.73	1.73
			2.11		1.73	
			2.1		1.73	
			2.11		1.73	
			2.1		1.73	

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More information about the project can be found at
co2-spicer.geology.cz.

PROJECT PARTNERS

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